

India should Implement a water recycling system

Imagine lining up in huge lines to get water each day. Imagine having to ration water and not be able to drink freely. Well unfortunately in India this is an unfortunate reality. People are thirsting right now. Water is the source of all life and without it we cannot live. A call to action must start now. This article will discuss the problems with India's water supply and how we can fix them.

India's water system may be among one of the worst in the world. The water is not up to health standards and cities such as Chennai have already experienced a day zero. Meaning that they did not have a single drop of water. The cause behind this is India completely overlooking the subject. India has one of the best power and electricity systems on earth that has never experienced an outage even during major storms because of how much they have invested in it. India definitely has the money and resources to work on their water system. With Mumbai (A city in India) making 310 billion USD per year. Let that sink in. That is just a single city. Opposing Viewpoint: Some people say that they should continue to build the rest of the infrastructure but I believe that human welfare Trumps that. ***The Solution:** Implement a water recycling system. Implementing a water recycling system would bring the water up to standards and reduce water shortages.* Opposing Viewpoint: Others think that halting work to work on the water system would cause a huge collapse but this is not true as we can go one city at a time to minimize the effect.

People are suffering right now and we need to take a stand so let's petition for an Indian water recycling system.

Work Cited

PM India. "Water Quality." PM India,

[https://phewater.assam.gov.in/how-to/test-water-quality-0#:~:text=To%20know%20the%20water%20quality.Divisional%20Level%20Laboratory%20\(SDLL\).](https://phewater.assam.gov.in/how-to/test-water-quality-0#:~:text=To%20know%20the%20water%20quality.Divisional%20Level%20Laboratory%20(SDLL).)